

Manganese (II) Complexes—Coordination Number 8

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Dihalo (chloro and bromo) tetrakis-thiourea manganese (II) complexes were reacted separately with 4-methyl pyridine and 4-vinyl pyridine and four eight-coordinated manganese (II) complexes having the formula $(Mntu_4X_2L_2)^o$ where X is halogen and L is substituted pyridine were isolated and characterised. The I. R. spectra indicate the presence of both bonded thiourea and substituted pyridine. They are non-electrolytes and paramagnetic indicating the presence of 5 unpaired electrons. These compounds are few more examples for this less common octa-coordination.

Many hexa-coordinated compounds of divalent manganese were reported¹ in the literature. Tetra-coordination is not very common but Gill, Nyholm and Pauling had shown² the compound $(Ph_3MeAs)_2MnCl_4$ to be tetrahedral. We had earlier reported some octahedral³ and tetrahedral⁴ complexes of manganese(II). More recently, eight-coordinated complexes having the formula $[Mntu_4Py_2X_2]$ where X is Cl^- or Br^- have been characterised and reported by us.⁵ Since octa-coordination for manganese(II) is very uncommon, we continued our investigations to isolate some more well-defined complexes exhibiting this unusual coordination number. Encouraged by our previous work⁵, dihalo tetrakis-thiourea manganese(II) compounds were reacted with substituted pyridines and four more octa coordinated manganese(II) complexes are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dihalo tetrakis-thiourea manganese(II) compounds are prepared according to known methods⁶. The Fluka pure samples of the substituted pyridines have been used. The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating metal, halogen and nitrogen. The conductance measurements were carried out in acetone medium using a Toshniwal Conductivity bridge type CLO102 and a dip-type cell. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens at room temperature using Gouy method. The infra-red spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP200 double beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics in the region $5000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

1. *Dichloro tetrakis-thiourea bis-(4-methyl pyridine) manganese (II)*, $[Mntu_4Cl_2(4-MePy)_2]^o$. To the hot solution of $Mntu_4Cl_2$ (1 g.) in the mixed solvent (40 ml) of carbon tetrachloride and ethanol (1:1), 4-methyl pyridine (0.5 ml) was added. The resulting solution on cooling gave beautiful needle shaped white crystalline compound. This was

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suction filtered, washed with CCl_4 and petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. (Found: Mn-8.7, Cl-11.4, N-21.8; $\text{MnC}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{10}\text{S}_4\text{Cl}_2$ requires: Mn-8.9, Cl-11.5 and N-22.7%). The compound melts at 158° . It is soluble in alcohol, nitrobenzene and acetone. The molar conductance in acetone (0.001 M) at 25° is 25.2 mhos. The compound is paramagnetic in solid form indicating the presence of 5 unpaired electrons. ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=6.3$ B.M.)

2. *Dichlorotetrakis-thiourea bis-(4-vinyl pyridine)manganese(II)*, $[\text{Mntu}_4\text{Cl}_2(4\text{-Vpy})_2]^\circ$ This was isolated as light yellow crystalline compound in the same way as the corresponding 4-methyl pyridine complex by using Mntu_4Cl_2 (1 g.) and 4-vinyl pyridine (0.5 ml). (Found: Mn-8.6, Cl-11.2, N-21.0; $\text{Mn C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{10}\text{S}_4\text{Cl}_2$ requires: Mn-8.6, Cl-11.1 and N-21.8%). The compound melts at 147° . It is soluble in alcohol, acetone and nitrobenzene. It is essentially a non-electrolyte in acetone medium, Λ_{M} being 27.8 mhos. The compound is paramagnetic in solid form indicating the presence of five unpaired electrons. ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=6.2$ B.M.).

3. *Dibromo tetrakis-thiourea bis-(4-methyl pyridine) manganese (II)*, $[\text{Mntu}_4\text{Br}_2(4\text{-MePy})_2]^\circ$. To the hot solution of Mntu_4Br_2 (1 g.) in the mixed solvent (30 ml) of ethanol and carbon tetrachloride (1:1), 4-methyl pyridine (0.4 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed for half an hour. On cooling, white micro crystalline compound separated. This was suction filtered, washed with CCl_4 and petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*. (Found: Mn-7.6, Br-22.6; $\text{Mn C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{10}\text{S}_4\text{Br}_2$ requires: Mn-7.8 and Br-22.7%). The compound decomposes at 160° . It is soluble in alcohol, nitrobenzene and acetone. The molar conductance in acetone (0.001 M) at 25° is 30.8 mhos. It is paramagnetic in solid form indicating the presence of five unpaired electrons ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=5.96$).

4. *Dibromo tetrakis-thiourea bis-(4-vinyl pyridine) manganese(II)*, $[\text{Mntu}_4\text{Br}_2(4\text{-Vpy})_2]^\circ$. This light yellow crystalline compound was prepared in the same way as the corresponding 4-methyl pyridine complex by using Mntu_4Br_2 (1 g.) and 4-vinyl pyridine (0.5 ml). (Found: Mn-7.2, Br-21.8; $\text{Mn C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{10}\text{S}_4\text{Br}_2$ requires: Mn-7.5, Br-21.9%). The compound decomposes at 160° . It is soluble in alcohol, nitrobenzene and acetone. The conductance measurements in acetone medium ($\Lambda_{\text{M}}=32.0$ mhos) reveal an essentially non-electrolytic nature. It is paramagnetic in solid form indicating the presence of five unpaired electrons. ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=6.1$ B.M.).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the four complexes reported now are well defined crystalline compounds with sharp and low melting points. They are all spin-free and the magnetic measurements indicate the presence of five unpaired electrons. This is compatible with tetra-, hexa- and octa-coordination arising out of the use of $4s4p^34d^2$ or $4s4p^34d^4$ hybrid bonding orbitals. The presence of six coordinated ligands as evidenced by analysis and I.R. spectra rules out the possibility of tetra-coordination. The coordination number of the metal ion can be six provided the halogen remains in the ionic state outside the coordination sphere as $[\text{Mntu}_4\text{L}_2]\text{X}_2$. In such a case the compounds should be 1 : 2 electrolytes. Even for 1:1 electrolytes, the Λ_{M} values in acetone medium will be as high as 150 mhos and the low values obtained now show that they are essentially non-electrolytes. Further, these compounds melt at a low temperature and are fairly soluble in organic solvents indicating the absence of an ionic form. Hence, the hexa-coordination is also ruled out.

When $Mntu_4X_2$ was reacted with substituted pyridine any of the three following possibilities may take place:

1. no reaction may occur leaving $Mntu_4X_2$ unchanged.
2. thiourea may be replaced completely or partially by substituted pyridine, or
3. substituted pyridine may be simply added on to the complex, without replacing thiourea.

The presence or absence of coordinated ligands can be known by studying the infra-red absorption spectra of the isolated complexes which are recorded in table 1. The spectra of the free ligands are also given for the sake of comparison.

TABLE I

Infra-red spectra of Octa-coordinated Manganese (II) complexes (cm^{-1}).

Ligands	[$Mntu_4X_2L_2$] ^o				Complexes	
			X=Cl L=4-McPy	X=Br L=4-McPy	X=Cl L=4-VPy	X=Br L=4-VPy
tu	4-McPy	4-VPy				
740 (s)	742 (s)	808 (s)	*730 (s)	*720 (s)	*734 (vs)	*730 (vs)
1095 (s)	823 (vs)	852 (vs)	740 (s)	730 (vs)	800 (s)	780(w)
1420 (s)	1015 (vs)	950(s)	818 (vs)	815 (vs)	840 (vs)	800 (s)
1476 (w)	1060 (m)	1010(vs)	825 (s)	828 (sh)	878 (s)	850 (vs)
1610 (s)	1235 (s)	1081 (w)	1025 (s)	1025 (vs)	940 (vs)	880(s)
	1430 (w)	1230 (m)	*1090 (vs)	*1080 (s)	1000 (s)	945 (vs)
	1460 (w)	1245 (m)	1210 (w)	*1095 (sh)	1020 (vs)	1010(s)
	1610 (vs)	1422 (vs)	1230 (s)	1220 (s)	*1080 (s)	1025 (s)
		1508 (s)	1420 (s)	1235 (vs)	1220 (s)	1100 (vs)
		1558 (s)	1610 (vs)	1620 (vs)	1420 (s)	1235 (m)
		1600 (vs)			1500 (m)	1422(m)
					1540 (s)	1510 (w)
					1602 (vs)	1560 (s)
						1630 (vs)

s-sharp, vs-very sharp, w-weak, m-medium, sh-shoulder.

*-denotes thiourea absorption bands.

A glance at this table brings out clearly the fact that both the thiourea and substituted pyridine are present bonded to the metal. Some absorption bands are masked in the Nujol absorption region. The substituted pyridines are liquid ligands and they cannot anyway remain in the free state in a solid complex compound. The characteristic thiourea absorption bands in the complexes are marked with asterisk. No definite comment can be made about the 1610 cm^{-1} absorption band since both thiourea and substituted pyridines absorb in this region. There are definite shifts in the bands due to both thiourea and substituted pyridines which is once again indicative of their coordination to the metal.

The analytical, spectral and conductance data of the compounds therefore definitely show that the compounds reported now are octa-coordinated manganese(II) complexes. Two different shapes have been proposed for the coordination number 8—square antiprism or dodecahedron. It was originally believed that this coordination number was rather unusual and limited to a very few compounds like $[TaF_8]^{3-}$ and $[Mo(CN)_8]^{4-}$.

Recently, however, more examples have been cited. Thus by crystallisation of bis (dibenzoylmethanato) zinc(II) from 4-methyl pyridine, a tetra (4-methyl pyridine) adduct was reported⁷ as a 8-coordinated compound of zinc(II). Divalent manganese was also shown⁸ to form 8-coordinate complexes with oxine, $Mn(C_9H_6NO)_2 \cdot 2C_9H_7NO$; and thioxine, $Mn(C_9H_6NS)_2 \cdot 2C_9H_7NS$. The compounds reported now appear to be few more examples for this unusual coordination number eight. X-ray crystallographic studies on these compounds will be very fruitful to establish the exact preferred stereochemistry.

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